

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

The prognostic value of cardiac biomarkers in predicting cardiovascular outcomes

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

The prognostic value of cardiac biomarkers in predicting cardiovascular outcomes.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This study is a retrospective, observational, data-linkage investigation that aims to evaluate the predictive capacity of cardiac biomarkers in assessing cardiovascular outcomes and survival among patients being evaluated for kidney transplantation in Scotland over a period of 10 years.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

Quantitative data will be collected from electronic health records and blood samples:

- Pseudonymised blood samples taken and stored at the time of each patient's first transplant assessment will be re-analysed for cardiac biomarkers of interest (hs-cTnI, hs-cTnT, NT-proBNP, hs-CRP);
- Biomarker results will be linked to patient outcomes derived from routinely collected healthcare data.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

This study will use existing datasets and blood samples from patients stored in the Scottish National Safe Haven (NSH) to develop a clinical risk prediction model. It is known that NT-proBNP and hs-cTn levels can predict outcomes in patients with kidney failure. However, no studies have yet looked at how these biomarkers should be used to assess cardiovascular risk in patients referred for kidney transplantation.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

All data will be held, and analysis carried out within the National Safe Haven secure analytical platform. Only aggregate data will be released after evaluation and approval by the electronic Data Research & Innovation Service team, in accordance with Public Health Scotland's Statistical Disclosure Policy. This data will be stored in non-specialist file formats, such as .txt, .csv, .xls, to facilitate sharing and ensure long-term accessibility of the data.

Aggregate data from ~ 2200 patients + administrative general data: < 100GB

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

All data will be collected, managed and stored in compliance with the requirements of the Joint Code of Practice for Research, BBSRC's Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice and the National Safe Haven security standards. Data collection and generation standards are set by the National Safe Haven teams. Approved data scientists work with regional Safe Haven hubs to access the "raw" data to produce clean, defined and linked datasets. This procedure is standardised. Validation checks are carried out regularly by Public Health Scotland. Access to electronic health record data is granted after a formal application to the NHS Scotland Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care. The CHI number is used to link to primary and secondary care databases, and the data generated will be stored and analysed in the National Safe Haven, with secure access granted to researchers. Only the anonymised and aggregate data will leave the National Safe Haven and will be stored on local networked data storage.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Data released for sharing will be validated and verified in accordance with accepted best practices. Data will be accompanied by the contextual information or documentation (metadata) needed to provide all necessary details on the origin and manipulation of the data to a secondary user in order to prevent misuse, misinterpretation, or confusion. To enable easier use and comparison by researchers, the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) (cdisc.org/standards) will be adopted.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

Any newly created data will be stored with relevant and appropriate metadata in a de-identified format for reuse for a minimum of 10 years in alignment with the BBSRC Statement on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice. We will use the local repository to preserve the data for the long term. It is fully encrypted and provides access controls to ensure that only nominated individuals can access data stored in the vault.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

We acknowledge and support the BBSRC policy on data sharing, which is essential for expediting the translation of research into products, intervention strategies, procedures, and policies to improve human health and welfare. The TRE datasets cannot be shared

as these are entrusted public health records, but summary-level and newly created data will be made available through an open share repository, except if the data is considered sensitive to the research and not suitable for open access or if specific embargo periods have been agreed upon.

(Q10) When will data be available?

The University expects its researchers to make relevant data openly available to other researchers in a timely way. The data will be archived and available for sharing but will be embargoed until a year after the publication of the main study papers. Until then, the study team will have exclusive use of the data.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

Data will be documented and saved in standard, machine-readable formats, facilitating long-term preservation and access. This approach guarantees that data remains usable and accessible for future research and verification. In due course, analysis of collected data will be published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at national and international meetings. Upon accepting the data, the repositories will supply a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and suggested citations for anyone citing this data in the future.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Appropriate metadata will be published with the research data to ensure reusability and enable other researchers to identify whether the data could be suitable for their own research. The published outputs will be assigned a DOI, which can be used to reference the data in publications.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

It is recognised that some restrictions may be necessary, e.g. to protect intellectual property, respect confidentiality, or honour third-party agreements, but these should be minimised as far as is practicable. It is also recognised that allowing a limited period of privileged access to the data may be appropriate for the research team that acquired or created it.

(Q14) Secondary use

This novel study will be the first to examine the utility of cardiac biomarkers in assessing future cardiovascular risk in patients referred for kidney transplantation. These tests are routinely used worldwide, meaning this study's findings will be clinically relevant, providing an accessible, affordable and patient-friendly way of accurately determining cardiovascular risk prior to transplantation. Sharing our data and files will enable other researchers to conduct further analyses and may answer questions beyond their original purpose.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

Secure access to national administrative and health data is provided through the Scottish National Safe Haven (NSH), a trusted research environment (TRE) provided by the EPCC at the University of Edinburgh and operated by eDRIS. The NSH meets several national and international security standards (ISO 27001:2013, Cyber Essentials, NHS England's Digital Security Protection Toolkit, and Digital Economy Act (2017) accredited), and penetration testing is performed on an annual basis.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

When accessing secure personal data, it is vital to protect the rights and freedoms of those individuals whose data is being accessed and to comply with the UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR) and Data Protection Act 2018. All data transfer into the National Safe Haven is performed by eDRIS staff via a secure file transfer process. Any outputs requested by researchers are subject to strict statistical checking and disclosure assessment to ensure that no individuals can be identified and that the outputs meet the highest confidentiality standards. Data will be pseudonymised by generating a study ID and linking this to the patient's identifiable CHI number in a link table. This will be created and stored on secure, password-protected NHS servers. Clinical data will be passed to the researchers linked to the study number with no patient identifiers. Data generated through the project will be stored securely, encrypted and annotated by study number, with no patient identifiers. Software- and/or hardware-encrypted password-protected dedicated study laptops and/or tablets will be used.

(Q17) Capabilities

The project will use the local repository's storage and computation resources, which will also provide long-term preservation of and access to the data. No costs beyond those built into the project application are anticipated to provide sustained access to all data and software. The data manager, funded entirely by the project grant, will manage the data and the ingest process.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

The data manager and the principal investigator are pivotal in the initial implementation and ongoing review and revision of the Data Management Plans (DMPs), ensuring these documents are current and comprehensive.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The institute is focusing on work to reduce carbon emissions and embed climate and sustainability into research, teaching, governance, operations, and partnerships. The research team will receive training on energy, climate, and biodiversity-related environmental issues. The practice of sharing protocols, research material such as code, and results contributes to collective work and avoids waste in the form of duplicate efforts.

(Q20) Responsibilities

Research Staff: Every member of the research team is responsible for the management, metadata creation, data security, and quality of their own data. This personal accountability ensures that data handling practices meet the research project's standards from the ground up. The principal investigator has overarching responsibility for ensuring the integrity and security of the data collected and stored throughout the research project. This includes overseeing data management practices and ensuring compliance with data protection regulations. The IT team is responsible for ensuring the data is properly secured and backed up regularly, in line with PI and the Institute's Data Manager expectations.